

DIAGNOSTIC AND TREATMENT KNOWLEDGE OF BREAST CANCER AMONG HEALTH PROFESSIONALS

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ABSTRACT

OBJECTIVE: To evaluate the knowledge of breast cancer diagnosis and treatment among female health professionals in a government health institution in Sagamu, Ogun State, Nigeria.

DESIGN: Descriptive study.

SETTING: Olabisi Onabanjo University Teaching Hospital (OOUTH), Sagamu, Ogun State, Nigeria.

SUBJECTS: One hundred and sixty two female health professionals.

RESULTS: Study population comprised of doctors (9.3%), nurses (78.4%) and Pharmacists, radiographers and lab scientists (P/L/R) (12.3%) with mean age of 32.97 ± 0.92 . The practice durations of the respondents ranged from 0 – 10 years (46.3%) and above 30 years (9.9%). The doctors and the P/L/R had 100% knowledge while the nurses had 96.9% as regards early diagnosis of breast cancer improving survival. The nurses had a higher knowledge (98%) in response to breast cancer can be treated surgically while the doctors had the least knowledge (86.6%), p value=0.021. Knowledge of these professional was also very satisfactory with years of practice as those of above 21years experience had higher knowledge when compared with lower years of experience.

CONCLUSION: This study indicated that these female health professionals had a very satisfactory diagnostic and treatment knowledge which is higher than some earlier studies. This knowledge though commendable should be improved upon through consistent education of these professionals.

KEYWORDS: Breast cancer, diagnosis and treatment, Health professionals, Teaching hospital.

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INTRODUCTION

Cancer is the leading cause of death worldwide, accounting for 7.6 million deaths in 2008 (WHO 2012). It is the most common type of cancer and the most common cause of cancer-related mortality among women worldwide (Hortobagyi et al., 2005). Women have one in eight risk of having breast cancer during their lifetime and early detection through screening is the only way to reduce morbidity and mortality (Akhigbe and Omuemu 2009, Beydağ and Yürügen 2010). Studies from Nigeria (Solanke and Adebamowo 1996) and other low income countries (Zanetti et al., 2010) indicate that breast cancer is now the most common female malignancy, having overtaken cervical cancer.

Early detection and treatment of breast cancer is associated with better chance of long-term survival (Parkin et al., 2002). In Nigeria, about two-third of patients with this disease present with advanced stages when therapy offers minimal benefit (Adebamowo and Ajayi 2000, Anyanwu 2000). Reports from Western Europe and North America revealed reduction in mortality from breast cancer due to adoption of screening methods for early detection of diseases (Parkin et al., 2002, Olsen et al., 2005).

In a study on Knowledge of breast cancer and its early detection measures among rural women in Akinyele Local Government Area, Ibadan, Nigeria, it was observed that rural women lacked appropriate information about breast cancer and its early detection measures. The finding that the major sources of information about breast cancer were "elders, neighbours and friends" suggests that health care workers are yet to succeed in their role of providing health information (Oluwatosin and Oladepo 2006).

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A study conducted in Benin City on knowledge, attitudes and practice of breast cancer screening among female health workers, revealed poor knowledge and the screening methods as well as low level of practice of breast cancer screening among these health workers. (Akhigbe and Omumu 2009). Expert opinion suggests that earlier discovery and treatment would favourably impact mortality rates from breast cancer (Anyanwu 2008, Anderson et al., 2003). Studies from some countries show that attitude and knowledge of healthcare providers are important determinants of using screening program and female health workers play an important role in creating an environment supportive of screening behaviours by offering positive role models (Bekker et al., 1999, Coleman et al., 2003).

Since there is no definitive cure for this disease, early detection through screening is vitally important in order to derive maximum benefit from available treatments and thus reduce mortality.

In view of the large proportion of patients with breast cancer in Nigeria presenting with advanced stages of the disease, there is need for more awareness of measures for early detection. Adequate knowledge and positive attitude towards breast cancer screening are essential for female healthcare professionals if they are to play their expected role in breast cancer awareness campaign in Nigeria.

This study was designed to evaluate the knowledge of breast cancer diagnosis and treatment among female health professionals in a government health institution in Sagamu, Ogun State, Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The population of this study comprised female health professionals in Olabisi Onabanjo University Teaching Hospital (OOUTH), located in Sagamu, Ogun State. The categories of female health professionals included medical doctors, pharmacists, nurses, radiographers and laboratory scientists. Of the 170 copies of questionnaire administered 162 were retrieved giving a 95%. There was no strict parameter on the choice of female health professionals that were given the questionnaire apart from the fact that they were currently employed by the management of the institution and also that they were on duty at the time of the study. Males, females that were on vacation, other casuals, administrative staff members and those who refused to participate were excluded from the study.

Ethical issues

Consent to administer the questionnaire was obtained from the appropriate authorities of the hospital before its administration. Maximum confidentiality of information was assured by excluding the names of the respondents or any information that could be linked to anybody.

Questionnaire design

This was a cross-sectional descriptive prospective study and the primary instrument for the collection of data was a pre-tested, self-administered questionnaire developed by the researcher. Questions were partly drawn using information on breast cancer from the literature text. Additional questions were adapted after modifications from questionnaires used in similar studies conducted previously in the country.

The questionnaire was divided into 3 sub-sections namely demographic information of the respondents, knowledge of breast cancer diagnosis and treatment and knowledge based on duration of practice.

Data analysis

Responses to questionnaire were entered into Microsoft Excel for sorting and SPSS version 16 was used for further analysis. Data was analysed using descriptive and comparative analyses. At 95% confidence interval, any P value of ≤ 0.05 was considered significant.

RESULTS

Respondent's demographics characteristics

Out of the 170 questionnaires administered to the respondents, 162 were correctly filled and retrieved, giving a percentage of 95% retrieval. The study population comprised doctors (9.3%), nurses (78.4%) and Pharmacists, radiographers and lab scientists (12.3%). The mean age of the respondents was 32.97 ± 0.92 (mean $\pm$ SEM). The

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married percentage was 76.5 while 78.4% practiced Christianity as a religion. The practice durations of the respondents ranged from 0 – 10 years (46.3%) and above 30 years (9.9%) (Table 1).

Correct knowledge of breast cancer diagnosis and treatment among respondents.

The doctors and the P/L/R had 100% knowledge while the nurses had 96.9% in the question: Early diagnosis of breast cancer improves survival with no statistical significance but the responses to; If detected early breast cancer has a very high five year survival rate gave percentage knowledge of 46.7, 75.6, and 80 among doctors, nurses and P/L/R group respectively with statistical significance (p value=0.044). The nurses had a higher knowledge (98%) in response to breast cancer can be treated surgically by removing the lumps while the doctors had the least knowledge (86.6%) with a p value=0.021. Again doctors had the 100% knowledge in response to the question: Radiotherapy is a form of treatment of breast cancer with P/L/R group having the least (70%) (p value=0.036). The total respondents mean knowledge of diagnosis was 78.6% Mean $\pm$ SD = 0.79 $\pm$ 0.41). There was no statistical significance on the knowledge of diagnosis based on the categories with $X^2=9.224$ df = 2 p value=0.72 (Table 2).

Respondents correct knowledge of diagnosis and treatment based on duration of practice

Those with 21-30years and above 30years experience had 100% knowledge in answer to: Early diagnosis of breast cancer improves survival, Mammography is a method of determining breast cancer, BSE should be carried out at least once in a month and Breast cancer can be treated surgically by removing the lumps while those with 11-20years of experience had the least knowledge of 94.5%, 85.4% and 87.3% respectively in the first three questions but none was statically significant. Those with over 30years experience also had 100% knowledge in the area of: Breast biopsy is the removal of breast tissue to examine it for breast cancer and Chemotherapy can be used in treatment of breast cancer with respective P-values of 0.001 and 0.040. The mean knowledge score of treatment was 92.3% (Mean $\pm$ SD = 0.92 $\pm$ 0.27). Based on duration of practice, there was no statistical significance in the overall knowledge of diagnosis with $X^2 = 17.202$ df = 3 p value =0.29 (Table 3).

Table1: SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPONDENTS

	Doctors	Nurses	Pharmacist/ Lab scientist/ Radiographer	Total (%)
	15 (9.3)	127(78.4)	20(12.3)	162(100)
	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)
<i>Age</i>				
20 – 30 years	2 (1.2)	37 (22.8)	11 (6.8)	50 (30.9)
31 – 40 years	7 (4.3)	43 (26.5)	6 (3.7)	56 (34.5)
41 – 50 years	3 (1.9)	26 (16.0)	3 (1.9)	32 (19.8)
51 – 60 years	3 (1.9)	11 (6.8)	-	14 (8.6)
Above 60 years	-	10 (6.2)	-	10 (6.2)
Mean Age $\pm$ SEM = 32.97 $\pm$ 0.92				
<i>Marital status</i>				
Married	12 (7.4)	101 (62.3)	11 (6.8)	124 (76.5)
Single	3 (1.9)	26 (16.0)	9 (5.6)	38 (23.5)
<i>Religion</i>				
Christianity	10 (6.2)	101 (62.3)	16 (9.9)	127 (78.4)
Muslim	5 (3.1)	26 (16.0)	4 (2.5)	35 (21.6)
Traditional Worshipper	-	-	-	-
<i>Duration of practise</i>				
0 – 10 years	7 (4.3)	53 (32.7)	15 (9.3)	75 (46.3)
11 – 20 years	5 (3.1)	45 (27.8)	5 (3.1)	55 (33.9)
21 – 30 years	3 (1.9)	13 (8.0)	-	16 (9.9)
Above 30 years	-	16 (9.9)	-	16 (9.9)

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Table 2: RESPONDENTS CORRECT KNOWLEDGE OF BREAST CANCER DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT

DIAGNOSIS	Doctors (n=15) No (%)	Nurses (n=127) No (%)	P/L/R (n=20) No (%)	Total (162) No (%)	p-value
Early diagnosis of breast cancer improves survival	15 (100.0)	123 (96.9)	20 (100.0)	158 (97.5)	0.568
If detected early breast cancer has a very high five year survival rate	7 (46.7)	96 (75.6)	16 (80.0)	119 (73.5)	0.044
Breast self-examination (BSE) is a way to find or diagnosed breast cancer	13 (86.7)	117 (92.1)	18 (90.0)	148 (91.4)	0.756
Mammography is a method of determining breast cancer	15 (100.0)	114 (89.8)	17 (85.0)	146 (90.1)	0.324
Breast biopsy is the removal of breast tissue to examine it for breast cancer	15 (100.0)	120 (94.5)	19 (95.0)	154 (95.1)	0.648
The practice of BSE is very easy and can be carried out by self	15 (100.0)	117 (92.1)	19 (95.0)	151 (93.2)	0.489
BSE should be carried out at least once in a month	15 (100.0)	119 (93.7)	17 (85.0)	151 (93.2)	0.195
Mammograms are not accessible, easy to use, and not cheap	12 (80.0)	86 (67.7)	12 (60.0)	110 (67.9)	0.453
Mammography is not a painful diagnosis	12 (80.0)	92 (72.4)	15 (65.0)	119 (73.5)	0.810
It is more effective than BSE in discovering lumps in the breast	12 (80.0)	121 (95.3)	19 (95.0)	152 (93.8)	0.065
TREATMENT					
Breast cancer can be treated surgically by removing the lumps	13 (86.6)	125 (98.4)	18 (90.0)	156 (96.3)	0.021
Lumpectomy and Mastectomy are types of surgery for breast cancer	15 (100.0)	122 (96.1)	17 (85.0)	154 (95.1)	0.068
Radiotherapy is a form of treatment of breast cancer	15 (100.0)	110 (86.6)	14 (70.0)	139 (85.8)	0.036
Chemotherapy can be used in treatment of breast cancer	13 (86.8)	119 (93.7)	17 (85.0)	149 (91.9)	0.301

P/L/R = Pharmacists, lab scientists and radiographers

BSE= Breast self-examination

Table 3: RESPONDENTS CORRECT KNOWLEDGE OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF BREAST CANCER BASED ON DURATION OF PRACTICE

DIAGNOSIS	0 - 10 years(n=75) Number (%)	11 - 20 years(n=55) Number (%)	21 - 30 years(n=16) Number (%)	Above 30 years(n=16) Number (%)	p-value
Early diagnosis of breast cancer improves survival	74 (98.7)	52 (94.5)	16 (100.0)	16 (100.0)	0.353
If detected early breast cancer has a very high five year survival rate	52 (69.3)	46 (83.6)	12 (75.0)	9 (56.3)	0.110
Breast self-examination (BSE) is a way to find or diagnosed breast cancer	71 (94.7)	46 (83.6)	15 (93.6)	16 (100.0)	0.078
Mammography is a method of determining breast cancer	67 (89.3)	47 (85.4)	16 (100.0)	16 (100.0)	0.179
Breast biopsy is the removal of breast tissue to examine it for breast cancer	72 (96.0)	54 (98.2)	12 (75.0)	16 (100.0)	0.001
The practice of BSE is very easy and can be carried out by self	75 (100.0)	48 (87.3)	15 (93.6)	15 (93.6)	0.165
BSE should be carried out at least once in a month	71 (94.6)	48 (87.3)	16 (100.0)	16 (100.0)	0.130
Mammograms are not accessible, easy to use, and cheap	47 (62.7)	39 (70.9)	13 (81.2)	11 (68.8)	0.478
Mammography is not a painful diagnosis	56 (74.7)	39 (70.9)	13 (81.2)	11 (68.8)	0.821
It is more effective than BSE is discovering lumps in the breast	68 (90.7)	53 (96.4)	16 (100.0)	15 (93.6)	0.398
TREATMENT					
Breast cancer can be treated surgically by removing the lumps	71 (94.6)	53 (96.4)	16 (100.0)	16 (100.0)	0.617
Lumpectomy and Mastectomy are types of surgery for breast cancer	72 (96.0)	53 (96.4)	14 (87.5)	15 (96.3)	0.504
Radiotherapy is a form of treatment of breast cancer	63 (84.0)	46 (83.6)	15 (93.6)	15 (96.3)	0.556
Chemotherapy can be used in treatment of breast cancer	72 (96.0)	46 (83.6)	15 (93.6)	16 (100.0)	0.040

DISCUSSION

The knowledge of diagnosis and treatment in this study group can be said to be very satisfactory across board with that of the doctors slightly higher while the other two groups are a par. This is consistent with earlier studies (Shiyam et al., 2009, Ibrahim and Odusanya 2009). The knowledge across board on early detection of breast cancer having a very high survival rate was lower than that obtained in a previous study in the same institution by Agboola et al., (2009). Majority believing that if breast cancer is diagnosed early, it improves the survival of the patient is also consistent with high knowledge obtained by Okobia et al., (2006), Madanat and Merril (2002) but very much higher than that gotten by Akhigbe and Omuemu (2009). Belief on breast self-examination (BSE) as a form of diagnosis or screening tool (91.4%) is higher than Okobia et al., (2006) in their study among community dwelling women with 87.2% knowledge score as well as with the result obtained by Chong et al., (2002) in Singapore. Regular BSE, should be encouraged as it is an easily applied, cheap, and effective routine screening method that enables a woman to realise any differences at an early stage.

It is however surprising to know that many of the doctors in this study did not know that early detection of breast cancer can lead to a higher survival rate. The doctors' knowledge (86.7%) was also poorer than the other groups on their response to: Breast self-examination (BSE) is a way to find or diagnosed breast cancer. This is consistent with the response obtained by Yeliz et al., (2011) where the doctors also got a poorer knowledge in

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response to their perceiving BSE as useful. There is need for effective education for this group since they occupy a strategic position in the health sector.

With respect to duration of practice, the knowledge of these professional was very satisfactory with years of practice impacting positively on knowledge. This is in contrast with Shiyam et al., (2009) who found clinical experience not influencing knowledge or practice. The knowledge about mammography though not statistically significant was excellent (100%) among those who had practiced from 21years and above as compared with those who had lower years of experience. This is similar to the findings of Akhigbe and Omuemu (2009) who found knowledge about mammography increased significantly from 16.8% in those who had practiced for 1–10 years to 44.0% among those who had practiced for more than 30 years, $p = 0.0079$. Belief in BSE once a month by participants is commendable as the knowledge is higher than that obtained by Agboola et al., (2009) but consistent with Ibrahim and Odusanya (2009) whose study participants actually practiced BSE. Female health professionals should be encouraged to practice self-breast examination (BSE) regularly as this will positively influence their role in motivating other women in the society who look upon them for advice and guidance in adopting the practice of screening methods.

Knowledge of mammography as a diagnostic method as well as it not being a painful diagnosis is very commendable in this study when compared to that had by Akhigbe and Omuemu (2009) where the respondents had a poor Knowledge. This result is however consistent with findings among public health nurses in Singapore (Chong et al., 2002) and by Ibrahim and Odusanya (2009).

Studies in developed countries show that attitude and orientation of healthcare providers are important determinants of use of breast cancer screening programs (Bekker et al., 1999, Lurie et al., 1997). In order to function as effective promoters of breast cancer control through early detection, health workers must possess the relevant knowledge as well as appropriate attitude and belief concerning the disease and its early detection (Roshan et al., 1994).

As yearly mammography and clinical breast exam has been cited as the single most important step that clinicians can take to reduce suffering and death from breast cancer (Smigal et al., 2006), healthcare providers should be equipped with adequate information about these screening and treatment methods. These will help to motivate patients' behaviours towards screening as well as improvement in treatment.

Knowledge about treatment of breast cancer was very satisfactory and compares with the work done by Shiyam et al., (2009) but higher than that found by Oluwatosin and Oladepo (2006). The belief by the respondents that breast cancer can be treated surgically is consistent with earlier studies (Ibrahim and Odusanya 2009). Although very satisfactory knowledge was obtained in virtually all the areas assessed the importance of continuous medical education for all healthcare professionals cannot be overemphasized for it is essential for them to be abreast with current information about important medical issues because of their roles as public educators.

CONCLUSSION

The result from this study indicated that these female health professionals had a very satisfactory diagnostic and treatment knowledge and a higher knowledge in most of their responses when compared to earlier studies. This level of knowledge though commendable should be improved upon through consistent education if the best is expected from them in their practice.

Breast self-examination (BSE), clinical breast examination (CBE) and mammography are recognised methods of screening for breast cancer and adoption of mammography screening has led to reduction in mortality from the disease in women over 50 years (Olsen et al., 2005). Considering the poor economy of our country, provision of facilities for routine mammography screening and other screening equipment at subsidized rates for women at risk is advocated.

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